

EXPLORATION AND GROUP ANALYSIS OF OCTAHEDRAL GROUP

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In this paper, we discuss a cube's rotation and spatial inversion symmetry. We explore the results in the form of representation matrices, multiplication tables, and the order of all group elements. Further, we present all combinations of generator elements, possible subgroups, conjugate classes, invariant subgroups, and their corresponding cosets, quotients, and homomorphic correspondences. Finally, we discuss the Cayley graph of the cube. This study develops the algebraic structure of a direct product of the symmetric group of order four and the cyclic group of order 2. The work offers a fascinating understanding of point groups for molecules resembling cubes and octahedrons. Researchers can better grasp the symmetries inherent in molecular structures by exploring the algebraic characteristics. This analysis helps understand the symmetry-dependent behaviors exhibited by the molecules.

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1. Introduction

Symmetry is a common phenomenon observed in nature. Various properties of elementary particles, atoms, and molecules are symmetric. Our primary focus is on the symmetry in structure of molecules. The rigid transformations under which the molecule remains invariant form a group structure[1]. Symmetry elements and operations characterize it. Symmetry elements are geometrical entities such as points, and lines of rotation and planes of reflection. Operations are transformations performed on the molecules against the symmetry elements, following which the molecule will slightly modify from the original state.

Operations are categorized into five primary types: identity, rotation, reflection, inversion, and improper rotation[2]. Symmetry elements intersect at a point which remains invariant under all the operations and hence form the point group of the molecule.

Every molecule possesses a particular point group, which helps us to understand its geometrical symmetry[3]. All the molecules are classified among the 32-point groups[4]. These are broadly categorized as linear, cyclic, dihedral, low symmetry, and high symmetry[5]. The point group symmetries are extensively used in nuclear structure calculations and atomic spectroscopy. The high-symmetry molecules, which happen to be one of the five platonic solids, are known for their unique structure and have a large number of symmetry operations.

Yu et al.(2019) have studied the characteristics of the point group generated by tetrahedron T_d [6]. They mentioned that contrary to the previous literature, which uses three generators for the group T_d , only two are enough to generate the entire group. Octahedral symmetry directly results from the symmetry transformations of a cube. As the cube and octahedron are duals of each other, they share the same point group represented by O_h [4].

The point group O_h is nonabelian; therefore, the character table contains multi-membered classes and degenerate irreducible representations. The point group has several symmetry elements of order three or higher, which are not co-axial. Therefore, it has at least three-dimensional irreducible representations. The symmetry described by the point group O_h may be termed isometric, as the three cartesian directions are degenerate. The point group O_h doesn't have a C_5 axis and is called cubic. Also, it has a four-fold axis of rotation, which is why O_h is called an octahedral group.

Based on the literature reviewed, a single coherent study presenting the characteristics of the symmetric group of a cube is yet to be defined, which motivates the current study. This article will focus on understanding the nature and properties of the Octahedral group, the symmetric group of Cube and Octahedron. We determine the matrix representations of the group O_h and form a theoretical proof exploring the nature of the cube's rotational group and total symmetry group. Lagrange's Theorem determines all subgroups of the symmetric groups of degrees 3 and 4 [7]. Building on the concept, subgroups of O_h obtained are isomorphic to the cyclic group of order 2 (Z_2), cyclic group of order 3 (Z_3), the cyclic group of order 4 (Z_4), Klein group (K_4), and dihedral groups D_n of order 6, 8 and 12.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we define the notation of vertices of the cube, which will be used throughout the manuscript unless specified otherwise. A cube is a platonic solid, having eight vertices, twelve edges, and six faces[7]. It is considered to be a highly symmetric object as the number of transformations under which the image is invariant is high, fourty eight to be precise.

Consider a cube having its center at the origin of \mathbb{R}^3 space, such that the coordinates of the related points chosen are :

$$A \rightarrow (-1, 1, 1), B \rightarrow (-1, -1, 1), C \rightarrow (1, -1, 1), D \rightarrow (1, 1, 1), E \rightarrow (-1, 1, -1), \\ F \rightarrow (-1, -1, -1), G \rightarrow (1, -1, -1), H \rightarrow (1, 1, -1).$$

A cube has three types of symmetry axes[5].

L passes through the center of the face and aligns with the coordinate axes, with the origin placed at the cube's center. There are three such symmetry axes. Cube rotates along these axes by 90° , 180° , 270° . The three axes with three rotations each give a total of 9 rotations.

M passes through the mid-point of opposite edges and is two-fold. There are four such axes. The cube rotates about these axes by 120° , 240° , which results a

Fig. 1. L axes of rotation

Fig. 2. M axes of rotation

Fig. 3. N axes of rotation

Fig. 4. The three axes of symmetry of cube

total of 8 rotations.

N passes through the two opposite vertices, and is two fold. There are six such axes. The cube rotates about these axes by 180° , which results 6 rotational elements.

All the rotational elements along with the identity element form a group.

2.1. Representation Matrices

Elements of permutation group can be represented in multiple ways[8]. As we are working with a three-dimensional structure, we aim to represent the elements in a matrix of order 3×3 .

Consider the transformation obtained by rotating the cube around x-axis by 90° . Let T be the transformation that represents this operation.

$$\text{Let } T = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{bmatrix}.$$

It is observed that it sends the point C (1,-1,1) to G(1,-1,-1), B(-1,-1,1) to F(-1,-1,-1) and H(1,1,-1) to D(1,1,1). Thus, the representation matrix is obtained as

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2.1}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2.2}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{2.3}$$

On solving the equations for all nine variables, the matrix obtained is

$L_{90}^x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. The name is interpreted as type L axis, along x direction and

rotated about 90° . Similarly, rotation about 180° and 270° , along the x direction gives the representation matrix

$$L_{180}^x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } L_{270}^x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The elements for rotating around y -axis for $90^\circ, 180^\circ, 270^\circ$ are

$$L_{90}^y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, L_{180}^y = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, L_{270}^y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The elements for rotating around z -axis for $90^\circ, 180^\circ, 270^\circ$ are

$$L_{90}^z = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, L_{180}^z = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, L_{270}^z = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The second set of symmetry axes obtained by joining the mid points of opposite edges. There are 6 such axes and each can be rotated by 180° . On rotating about these axes, we see that the following diagonals get exchanged: $A \longleftrightarrow B, A \longleftrightarrow D, A \longleftrightarrow E, B \longleftrightarrow C, B \longleftrightarrow D, C \longleftrightarrow D$. The matrix representations for these are given as

$$N_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, N_{13} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, N_{14} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$N_{23} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, N_{24} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, N_{34} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The third set of symmetry axes are the main diagonals of the cube obtained by joining the opposite vertices. There are four such diagonals labelled as 1 (yellow), 2(red), 3(blue), 4(green), and each can be rotated by 120° and 240° . The matrix

transformations obtained are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{120}^1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, M_{240}^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
 M_{120}^2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, M_{240}^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
 M_{120}^3 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, M_{240}^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
 M_{120}^4 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, M_{240}^4 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The transformations of reflection operators are formed from the 9 reflection planes observed in a cube.

Next, we obtain the reflection elements of the octahedral group. The horizontal plane is analogous to the xy plane in \mathbb{R}^3 and the vertical planes are analogous to the xz and yz planes in \mathbb{R}^3 .

The horizontal and vertical planes are shown in Figure 8. The transformation matrices obtained are

$$\sigma_h = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \sigma_v = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \sigma_v = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Fig. 5. Horizontal plane along xy plane

Fig. 6. Vertical plane along xz plane

Fig. 7. Vertical plane along yz plane

Fig. 8. Horizontal and vertical planes passing through the cube

There are 6 other reflection planes that pass through the opposite edges and are known as the dihedral planes. They are shown in Figure 9. The transformation matrices obtained are

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{V1} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, D_{V2} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\
D_{E1} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, D_{E2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
D_{E3} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, D_{E4} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned}$$

The other representation matrices that originate from the composition of reflection and rotation are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{90}^x &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{90}^x)^3 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{90}^y &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{90}^y)^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{90}^z &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{90}^z)^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{E1}^{12} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{E2}^{34} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{E2}^{34})^5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{E3}^{23} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
S_{E4}^{14} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, (S_{E4}^{14})^5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned}$$

2.2. Rotational Group of cube

Theorem 2.1. *If the group of rotations of a regular solid G_S acts faithfully on some set of features of a regular solid X , then G_S is a subgroup of S_X .*

Fig. 9. Dihedral planes passing through the cube

Proof - Let G_S be a rotational group of symmetry for some regular solid. Let X be some set of features of the regular solid, i.e., vertices, diagonals or inscribed cubes. Assume G_S acts faithfully which means that the only element of G_S that fixes every element of X is the identity.

Construct a homomorphism $\phi : G_S \rightarrow S_X$. We know this is a good map since we are permuting the elements of X . Consider the image of $\phi(G_S)$. We know the image is a subgroup of S_X , i.e., $\phi(G_S) \leq S_X$.

By first isomorphism theorem[9], $G_S / \text{Ker}\phi \cong \phi(G_S)$ [5]. If G_S acts on X faithfully then kernel is trivial.

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \frac{G_S}{\text{Ker}\phi} &\cong \phi(G_S) \leq S_X \\ \implies G_S &\leq S_X \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1 - The group of rotations of a regular cube G_C has 24 elements.

Proof: Consider a regular cube C . Fix a vertex a and find how many possible rotations are there that fix vertex a . This is same as finding $|G_a|$, the stabilizer of a . Since any vertex in cube touches exactly 3 faces and any rotation must send a face to face. We can rotate the cube in 3 different ways while keeping the vertex a fixed. i.e., $|G_a| = 3$. Now, since each vertex is isomorphic to every other vertex, vertex a can be mapped to any other 8 vertices. This is the orbit of a , so $|O_a| = 8$. By Orbit-Stabilizer Theorem, the order of the group of rotations = $|G_C| = 3 \times 8 = 24$ [10].

Theorem 2.2. The group of rotations of the cube is isomorphic to S_4 , symmetric group on set of size 4.

Proof: Let X be the set of four main diagonals of the cube. Let G_C act on X . Since the only element of G_C that fixes every diagonal is the identity, then G_C acts faithfully on X .

By Theorem 3.1, $G_C \leq S_4$. Since $|S_4| = 4! = 24$ and by Result 1, $|G_C| = 24$, we get that G_C is an improper subgroup of S_4 .

$$\implies G_C \cong S_4$$

Theorem 2.3. The total symmetry group of the cube O_h is isomorphic to $S_4 \times Z_2$.

Proof: We have established that the rotational group of cube, G_C is isomorphic to S_4 . Consider a set $S = \{E, I\}$, where E, I are functions from $\mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ defined as

$$E(x, y, z) = (x, y, z) \text{ and } I(x, y, z) = (-x, -y, -z)$$

Then S forms a group under composition of functions:

- (1) Closure - $E.E = E, E.I = I, I.E = I, I.I = E$
- (2) Associativity - Composition of two functions is associative.
- (3) Identity - It is clear that $\forall a \in S, a.E = E.a = a$. Thus, E is the identity element of S .
- (4) Inverse - We have $E.E = E$ and $I.I = E$. Therefore, an inverse element a^{-1} exists for all $a \in S$ such that $a.a^{-1} = E$.

Now, order of E is 1 and order of I is 2 and order of S is 2. Thus, $S \cong Z_2$.

Next, we have to show that O_h is a direct product of G_C and S . Consider the matrix representation of the elements of the group S .

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } I = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Consider the following result[10], "If H and K are subgroups of G , for which $HK = G$, if they have only the identity element in common and if every element of H commutes with every element of K , then $G \cong H \times K$."

The commutativity of elements of G_C with elements of S can be verified using the representation matrices obtained in section 2.1. Taking $G = O_h, H = G_C, K = S$, we know that every rotational group of regular solid is the subgroup of the total symmetry group of regular solid [9], i.e., $G_C \leq O_h$. As $S \subset O_h$ and S is a group, $S \leq O_h$. G_C being the group of rotations doesn't include the inversion element. Therefore, $G_C \cap S = \{E\}$

From the result mentioned above, we get $O_h \cong G_C \times S$ and as $G_C \cong S_4$, $S \cong Z_2$, we have $O_h \cong S_4 \times Z_2$

3. Main Results

In this section, we present our findings, focusing on the study of the characteristics of the octahedral group.

3.1. Multiplication Table

The multiplication table is table obtained using the representation matrices of symmetric groups[11]. We extend this application to the Octahedral group, which is a direct product of a symmetric group of order 4 with a cyclic group of order 2. Another way to verify that the set of all rotations and reflections forms a group is

by constructing a heat map of the cayley table. For the given set of representation matrices, we obtained the heat map as given in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Heat Map of Cayley Table

From the heat map, we observe that there are no white pixels present, which shows that the set of all representation matrices are closed under multiplication. The dark blue pixel, shown at the left end of the color range represents the identity element. We observe that it is present in every row and column, which confirms the existence of inverse element for each element in the set. The map isn't symmetric which shows that the group is not abelian.

Therefore, the set of all 48 representation matrices, of symmetry of cube forms a group known as the Octahedral Group.

3.2. Properties of Cube

3.2.1. Order of Elements

The order of each element is obtained from the multiplication table.

The elements

$L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, N_{12}, N_{13}, N_{14}, N_{23}, N_{24}, N_{34}, \sigma_h, \sigma_v, \sigma_v, DV_1, DV_2, DE_1, DE_2, DE_3, DE_4$ are of order 2. These correspond to cyclic groups of order 2 $\{E, a\}$ where a is an element from the above set.

The elements

$$M_{120}^1, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^4$$

are of order 3. These correspond to cyclic groups of order 3, $\{E, M_{120}^i, M_{240}^i\}$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

The elements

$$L_{90}^x, L_{270}^x, L_{90}^y, L_{270}^y, L_{90}^z, L_{270}^z, S_{90}^x, (S_{90}^x)^3, S_{90}^y, (S_{90}^y)^3, S_{90}^z, (S_{90}^z)^3$$

are of order 4. These correspond to cyclic groups of order 4, $\{E, L_{90}^i, L_{180}^i, L_{270}^i\}$, $i = x, y, z$.

The elements

$$S_{E1}^{12}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, S_{E2}^{34}, (S_{E2}^{34})^5, S_{E3}^{23}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5, S_{E4}^{14}, (S_{E4}^{14})^5$$

are of order 6. These correspond to cyclic groups of order 6.

3.2.2. Conjugacy classes

Let G be a group and $a \in G$. An element $b \in G$ is called a conjugate of a in G if $b = cac^{-1}$ for some $c \in G$.

A relation \equiv is defined on G as: $\forall a, b \in G, a \equiv b$ if $cac^{-1} = b$, for $c \in G$. Here, \equiv defines an equivalence relation on G . This relation is called conjugacy and the equivalence class $C_l = \{cac^{-1} | c \in G\}$ of a determined by \equiv is called the conjugacy class of a . Using this definition, an algorithm was constructed which helped us obtain the conjugacy classes of the group. The conjugacy classes are

- (1) $\{E\}$
- (2) $\{L_{270}^y, L_{90}^z, L_{90}^y, L_{270}^z, L_{90}^x, L_{270}^x\}$
- (3) $\{L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$
- (4) $\{N_{14}, N_{15}, N_{12}, N_{23}, N_{34}, N_{26}\}$
- (5) $\{M_{120}^1, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^4\}$
- (6) $\{I\}$
- (7) $\{\sigma_h, \sigma_{V2}, \sigma_{V1}\}$
- (8) $\{D_{E1}, D_{E2}, D_{E3}, D_{E4}, D_{V1}, D_{V2}\}$
- (9) $\{S_{90}^x, S_{270}^x, S_{90}^y, S_{270}^y, S_{90}^z, S_{270}^z\}$
- (10) $\{S_{E1}^{12}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, S_{E2}^{34}, (S_{E2}^{34})^5, S_{E4}^{14}, (S_{E4}^{14})^5, S_{E3}^{23}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5\}$

The inverse elements of these group elements in the conjugate class can also form a conjugate class and is called as reciprocal class with respect to the related conjugate class. On observation, we find that all the conjugacy classes of this group are self reciprocal.

3.2.3. Proper Subgroups

From Lagrange's Theorem[12], we know that the Octahedral Group will have subgroups of order 1,2,3,4,6,8,12,16,24,48[7].

- (1) The subgroups of order 1 and 48 are trivial.
- (2) The subgroups of order 2 are of the form $\{E, a\}$, where a is an element of order 2. There are 19 such subgroups. They are cyclic.
- (3) The subgroups of order 3 are of the form $\{E, b, b^2\}$, where order of b is 3. There are 4 such subgroups and they are cyclic.
- (4) The subgroups of order 4 are of the form $\{E, c, c^2, c^3\} \cong Z_4$, where order of c is 4; $(E, a, b, c) \cong K_4$, where order of a, b, c is 2 and (E, a, c, c^3) , where order of a is 2 and order of c is 4. There are 31 subgroups in total. The subgroups isomorphic to Z_4 are cyclic.
- (5) The subgroups of order 6 are of the form $\{E, a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2\}$, where a_i are of order 2 and b_i are of order 3. The other form is $(E, a_1, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2)$ where a_1 is of order 2, b_i is of order 3 and c_i is of order 6. These are non cyclic subgroups and there are 12 subgroups of order 6.
- (6) The subgroups of order 8 are of the form $\{E, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}$, where each a_i is of order 2 and $E, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, b_1, b_2$, where each a_i is of order 2 and each b_i is of order 4. There are 19 subgroups and they are non cyclic.
- (7) The subgroups of order 12 are of the form $\{E, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2\}$, where each a_i is of order 2 and each b_i is of order 3 and each c_i is of order 4. There are 5 such subgroups.
- (8) The subgroups of order 16 are of the form $\{E, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9, a_{10}, a_{11}, b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4\}$, where each a_i is of order 2 and each b_i is of order 4. There are 3 such subgroups.
- (9) The subgroups of order 16 are isomorphic to S_4 and $A_4 \times Z_2$. There are 3 such subgroups.

Table 1 illustrates the number of subgroup of each order and identify the groups they are isomorphic to.

3.2.4. Invariant Subspaces

Let H be a subgroup of G , and consider the set of elements defined as

$H_g = \{g^{-1}h_1g, g^{-1}h_2g, g^{-1}h_3g, \dots\}$ for some particular element g that is in G but not in H . This set also forms a subgroup of G . We shall see this by considering the group properties.

- (1) Product of any two elements in H are also in H . We have $g^{-1}h_i g \cdot g^{-1}h_j g = g^{-1}h_i h_j g$. The last quantity is in H since $h_i h_j$ must be in H .

Order of subgroup	Number of subgroups	Isomorphic to
1	1	{E}
2	19	Z_2
3	4	Z_3
4	31	$K_4 \times Z_2, K_4, Z_4$
6	12	Z_6, D_6
8	19	$D_8, Z_4 \times D_2, D_2 \times D_4$
12	5	A_4, D_{12}
16	3	$D_2 \times D_8$
24	3	$S_4, A_4 \times Z_2$
48	1	$S_4 \times Z_2$

Table 1. Subgroup Table

- (2) H contains the identity, since H (being a subgroup) contains the identity, and $g^{-1}Ig = g^{-1}g = I$.
- (3) Every element in H has an inverse, since the inverse of $g^1h_i g$ is $g^{-1}h_i^{-1}g$, and h_i^{-1} must be in H .
- (4) Multiplication is associative, since $(g^1h_i g \cdot g^1h_j g)g^1h_k g = g^{-1}h_i g(g^{-1}h_j g \cdot g^{-1}h_k g)$.

The subgroup H above is defined for one particular element g . Now suppose that no matter which element g we choose, the subgroups H and H_g are the same: $H = H_g, \forall g \in G$. In that case, H is called an invariant subgroup of G . The invariant subgroup can be obtained from the union of several conjugate classes, but there must be identity element existing in this set. Also, closure need to be satisfied and the order of invariant subgroup must be the divisor of the large group O_h 's counterpart.

The invariant subgroups obtained are

- (1) {E}
- (2) {E, I}
- (3) {E, $L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z$ }
- (4) {E, I, $L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, \sigma_h, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_{v2}$ }
- (5) {E, $L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, M_{120}^1, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^4$ }
- (6) {E, $L_{90}^x, L_{270}^x, L_{90}^y, L_{270}^y, L_{90}^z, L_{270}^z, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, N_{14}, N_{15}, N_{12}, N_{23}, N_{34}, N_{26}, M_{120}^1, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^4$ }
- (7) {I, $\sigma_{v2}, M_{120}^4, S_{E3}^{23}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, L_{180}^x, M_{240}^1, S_{E1}^{12}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5, M_{120}^1 \cdot \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_h, M_{240}^3, M_{240}^4, (S_{E2}^{34})^5, M_{120}^3, Z_{180}, E, (S_{E4}^{14})^5, S_{E3}^{34}, L_{180}^y, S_{E4}^{14}, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^2$ }
- (8) {E, $S_{90}^x, S_{270}^x, D_{E1}, D_{E2}, L_{180}^{Lx}, L_{90}^{Lx}, L_{180}^{Ly}, L_{180}^{Lz}, S_{E3}^{23}, N_{14}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, I, L_{270}^{Lz}, \sigma_{v1}, N_{26}, L_{270}^{Lx}, S_{E4}^{14}, \sigma_{v2}, N_{15}, \sigma_h, L_{90}^{Lz}$ }

(9) Octahedral Group O_h

3.2.5. Quotient Groups

Let G be a group and let H be a normal subgroup of G .

The set $G/H = \{aH | a \in G\}$ is a group under the operation $(aH)(bH) = abH$, known as factor group or quotient group.

Consider two cosets $\{L_{90}^x, S_{270}^x\}$ and $\{S_{90}^y, L_{270}^y\}$, corresponding to a subset H . Then, the product of two cosets is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \{L_{90}^x, S_{270}^x\} \cdot \{S_{90}^y, L_{270}^y\} &= \{L_{90}^x * S_{90}^y, L_{90}^x * L_{270}^y, S_{270}^x * S_{90}^y, S_{270}^x * L_{270}^y\} \\ &= \{S_{E3}^{23}, M_{240}^1, M_{240}^1, S_{E3}^{23}\} \\ &= \{S_{E3}^{23}, M_{240}^1\} \end{aligned}$$

The result of the product is another coset which is another coset of H .

Consider the invariant subgroup $H_1 = \{E, I\}$. Then, H_1 has $\frac{48}{2} = 24$ cosets, which forms a group under product of cosets defined above[14].

Among the 24 elements, there are 9 elements of order 2, 8 elements of order 2, 6 elements of order 4. Consequently, the group all cosets of $\{E, I\}$ is isomorphic to S_4 (symmetric group of order 12). The correspondence can be defined as

- | | |
|---|--|
| (1) $\{E, I\} \longleftrightarrow a_1$ | (14) $\{D_{E1}, N_{23}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{14}$ |
| (2) $\{L_{90}^x, S_{270}^x\} \longleftrightarrow a_2$ | (15) $\{D_{E3}, N_{34}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{15}$ |
| (3) $\{L_{180}^x, \sigma_{V2}\} \longleftrightarrow a_3$ | (16) $\{D_{V2}, N_{26}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{16}$ |
| (4) $\{S_{90}^x, L_{270}^x\} \longleftrightarrow a_4$ | (17) $\{M_{120}^1, (S_{E3}^{23})^5\} \longleftrightarrow a_{17}$ |
| (5) $\{L_{90}^y, S_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow a_5$ | (18) $\{S_{E3}^{23}, M_{240}^1\} \longleftrightarrow a_{18}$ |
| (6) $\{\sigma_{V1}, L_{180}^y\} \longleftrightarrow a_6$ | (19) $\{(S_{E2}^{34})^5, M_{120}^2\} \longleftrightarrow a_{19}$ |
| (7) $\{S_{90}^y, L_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow a_7$ | (20) $\{M_{240}^2, S_{E2}^{34}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{20}$ |
| (8) $\{S_{270}^z, L_{90}^z\} \longleftrightarrow a_8$ | (21) $\{(S_{E4}^{14})^5, M_{120}^3\} \longleftrightarrow a_{21}$ |
| (9) $\{L_{180}^z, \sigma_h\} \longleftrightarrow a_9$ | (22) $\{M_{240}^3, S_{E4}^{14}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{22}$ |
| (10) $\{S_{90}^z, L_{270}^z\} \longleftrightarrow a_{10}$ | (23) $\{M_{120}^4, (S_{E1}^{12})^5\} \longleftrightarrow a_{23}$ |
| (11) $\{N_{14}, D_{E2}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{11}$ | (24) $\{S_{E1}^{12}, M_{240}^4\} \longleftrightarrow a_{24}$ |
| (12) $\{N_{15}, D_{V1}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{12}$ | |
| (13) $\{D_{E4}, N_{12}\} \longleftrightarrow a_{13}$ | |

where a_i is an element of $S_4, \forall 1 \leq i \leq 24$.

Consider the invariant subgroup, $H_2 = \{E, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$. It has $\frac{48}{4} = 12$ cosets. The set of all the cosets of H_2 form a group under the product of cosets defined above.

Among the 12 elements, there are 1 element of order 1, 7 elements of order 2, 2 elements of order 3 and 2 elements of order 6. The group of cosets of $\{E, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ isomorphic to D_{12} (dihedral group of order 12). The correspondence between them can be viewed as

- | | |
|--|--|
| (1) $\{E, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^z, L_{180}^y\} \longleftrightarrow b_1$ | (8) $\{S_{270}^x, S_{90}^x, D_{E1}, D_{E2}\} \longleftrightarrow b_8$ |
| (2) $\{L_{90}^x, N_{14}, L_{270}^x, N_{23}\} \longleftrightarrow b_2$ | (9) $\{D_{E4}, S_{90}^y, D_{E3}, S_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow b_9$ |
| (3) $\{N_{12}, L_{90}^y, N_{34}, L_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow b_3$ | (10) $\{S_{90}^z, D_{V1}, D_{V2}, S_{270}^z\} \longleftrightarrow b_{10}$ |
| (4) $\{N_{15}, N_{26}, L_{270}^z, L_{90}^z\} \longleftrightarrow b_4$ | (11) $\{S_{E2}^{34}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5, S_{E4}^{14}, S_{E1}^{12}\} \longleftrightarrow b_{11}$ |
| (5) $\{M_{120}^1, M_{240}^4, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^2\} \longleftrightarrow b_5$ | (12) $\{(S_{E2}^{34})^5, S_{E3}^{23}, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, S_{E4}^{14}\} \longleftrightarrow b_{12}$ |
| (6) $\{M_{120}^2, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^1\} \longleftrightarrow b_6$ | |
| (7) $\{\sigma_h, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_{V2}, I\} \longleftrightarrow b_7$ | |

where b_i is an element of $S_4, \forall 1 \leq i \leq 24$

The group is defined as $\langle a, x | a^6 = x^2 = e, xax^{-1} = a^{-1} \rangle$. Therefore, a combination of any element from $b_2/b_3/b_4/b_7/b_8/b_9/b_{10}$ and b_{11}/b_{12} will generate this group of cosets of H_2 .

Consider the invariant subgroup $H_3 = \{E, I, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_{V2}, \sigma_h\}$. It has $\frac{48}{8} = 6$ cosets. The set of all the cosets of H_3 form a group under the product of cosets defined above.

Among the 6 elements, there are 1 element of order 1, 3 elements of order 2, 2 elements of order 3. The group of cosets of $\{E, I, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_{V2}, \sigma_h\}$ is isomorphic to D_6 (dihedral group of order 6). The correspondence between them can be viewed as

- | |
|--|
| (1) $\{L_{180}^x, L_{180}^z, \sigma_{V2}, I, E, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_h, L_{180}^y\} \longleftrightarrow c_1$ |
| (2) $\{S_{90}^x, L_{90}^x, S_{270}^x, L_{270}^x, D_{E1}, N_{23}, D_{E2}, N_{14}\} \longleftrightarrow c_2$ |
| (3) $\{S_{270}^y, N_{12}, L_{90}^y, D_{E3}, N_{34}, D_{E4}, S_{90}^y, L_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow c_3$ |
| (4) $\{D_{V2}, L_{90}^z, N_{15}, D_{V1}, N_{26}, L_{270}^z, S_{90}^z, S_{270}^z\} \longleftrightarrow c_4$ |
| (5) $\{(S_{E4}^{14})^5, M_{240}^2, S_{E1}^{12}, S_{E2}^{34}, M_{240}^4, M_{120}^3, (S_{E3}^{23})^5, M_{120}^1\} \longleftrightarrow c_5$ |
| (6) $\{(S_{E2}^{34})^5, S_{E3}^{23}, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^4, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, M_{120}^2, S_{E4}^{14}, M_{240}^3\} \longleftrightarrow c_6$ |

The group is defined as $\langle a, x | a^3 = x^2 = e, xax^{-1} = a^{-1} \rangle$. Therefore, a combination of $c_2/c_3, /c_4$ and c_5/c_6 will generate this group of cosets of H_3 .

Consider the invariant subgroup

$H_4 = \{E, L_{180}^x, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z, M_{120}^1, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^2, M_{120}^3, M_{240}^3, M_{120}^4, M_{240}^4\}$. It has $\frac{48}{12} = 4$ cosets. The set of all cosets of H_4 forms a group under the product of cosets defined above.

Among the 4 elements, there is 1 element of order 1 and 3 elements of order 2. The group of cosets of H_4 isomorphic to D_4 (dihedral group of order 4). The correspondence between them can be viewed as

- | |
|--|
| (1) $\{L_{180}^x, M_{240}^2, L_{180}^z, M_{240}^1, M_{120}^4, M_{120}^3, M_{120}^2, M_{240}^4, M_{120}^1, E, M_{240}^3, L_{180}^y\} \longleftrightarrow E$ |
|--|

- (2) $\{L_{90}^z, L_{90}^x, L_{270}^x, N_{12}, N_{15}, L_{90}^y, N_{23}, N_{34}, L_{270}^z, N_{26}, N_{14}, L_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow A$
- (3) $\{(S_{E4}^{14})^5, (S_{E2}^{34})^5, S_{E3}^{23}, \sigma_{V2}, S_{E1}^{12}, S_{E2}^{34}, S_{E4}^{14}, (S_{E3}^{23})^5, I, (S_{E1}^{12})^5, \sigma_{v1}, \sigma_h\} \longleftrightarrow B$
- (4) $\{S_{90}^x, D_{E4}, D_{V2}, S_{270}^x, D_{V1}, D_{E1}, D_{E3}, D_{E2}, S_{90}^z, S_{90}^y, S_{270}^z, S_{270}^y\} \longleftrightarrow C$

The other three invariant subgroups are of order 24 and have 2 cosets each. The group formed by cosets of the invariant subgroups of order 24 is isomorphic to Z_2 .

3.2.6. Generators

A subset of a group G is said to be a generating set if each and every element of the group can be expressed as a product of elements of the generating set, provided the set does not lie in a proper subgroup of the group[15]. Although the smallest generator set is of order 2, which contains a 6 order element and a 4 order element, we aim to construct the generator containing element from rotational group and/or the inversion element. This is because every 6 order element can be written as a product of a rotational element and inversion.

The smallest generating set from the rotational group for the total symmetric group of cube has 3 elements:

- (1) Type I - It contains 2 elements of order 2, one of which is the inversion element and another element of order 4.
- (2) Type II - It contains one element of order 3, and 2 elements of order 4.

Type I

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| (1) $\{I, L_{90}^z, L_{180}^y\}$ | (5) $\{I, L_{180}^x, L_{90}^x\}$ |
| (2) $\{I, L_{270}^z, L_{180}^y\}$ | (6) $\{I, L_{270}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ |
| (3) $\{I, L_{90}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (7) $\{I, L_{270}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (4) $\{I, L_{270}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | |

Type II

- | | | |
|---|--|--|
| (1) $\{M_{120}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (9) $\{M_{120}^2, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (17) $\{M_{240}^3, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (2) $\{M_{120}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ | (10) $\{M_{240}^2, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (18) $\{M_{240}^3, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (3) $\{M_{120}^1, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (11) $\{M_{240}^2, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ | (19) $\{M_{120}^4, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ |
| (4) $\{M_{240}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (12) $\{M_{240}^2, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (20) $\{M_{120}^4, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (5) $\{M_{240}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ | (13) $\{M_{120}^3, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (21) $\{M_{120}^4, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (6) $\{M_{240}^1, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (14) $\{M_{120}^3, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ | (22) $\{M_{240}^4, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ |
| (7) $\{M_{120}^2, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (15) $\{M_{120}^3, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ | (23) $\{M_{240}^4, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ |
| (8) $\{M_{120}^2, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^z\}$ | (16) $\{M_{240}^3, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$ | (24) $\{M_{240}^4, L_{180}^y, L_{180}^z\}$ |

3.3. Cayley Graph

Given a group G and its subset S , the Cayley Graph $C(G : S)$ is the undirected graph with vertex set G and an edge set containing vertex from $g \longrightarrow sg$ and $g \longrightarrow s^{-1}g$ whenever $g \in G$ and $s \in S$.

If $|g| = 2$, then $g \rightarrow sg$ and $g \rightarrow s^{-1}g$ are the same edge. $C(G : S)$ is connected if and only if S is a generating set of G .

To construct the Cayley graph of $S_4 \times Z_2$, we consider a subset S which doesn't contain the identity element. Let $S = \{I, L_{270}^x, L_{180}^z\}$, a generator of Type I. The Cayley graph $C(S_4 \times Z_2, (I, L_{270}^x, L_{180}^z))$ is

Fig. 11. $C(O_h : (I, L_{270}^x, L_{180}^z))$

Let $S = \{M_{120}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y\}$, a generator of Type II. The Cayley graph $C(S_4 \times Z_2, (M_{120}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y))$ is

Fig. 12. $C(O_h : (M_{120}^1, L_{90}^x, L_{180}^y))$

4. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we have provided proof that the symmetry group of the cube is isomorphic to $S_4 \times Z_2$, a direct product of the symmetric group of order 4 and cyclic group of order 2. We have presented the matrix representations of the elements of the octahedral group, O_h . We explored the representation of the Cayley table of the octahedral group with the help of a heat map. The heat map utilizes colors instead of group elements to verify that matrix representations obtained form a group. We discussed various characteristics of the octahedral group, such as the order of the elements, the conjugate classes, invariant subgroups, quotient groups, and homomorphic correspondence. We found the octahedral group O_h 's generators belong to the rotational group of the cube G_S . Finally, we concluded with the Cayley graph of the octahedral group, which is constructed by generators.

This study delves into the algebraic structure of $S_4 \times Z_2$, offering a fascinating understanding of point groups for molecules that resemble cube as well as octahedron. Researchers can better grasp the symmetries inherent in molecular structures by exploring the algebraic characteristics. This analysis helps understand the symmetry-dependent behaviors exhibited by the molecules. Consequently, this research contributes significantly to our comprehension of molecular symmetry and its implications in various fields, from chemistry to atomic spectroscopy.

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Conflict of interest statement

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest known.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article

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